

Indirect Complexometric Determination of Thallium using Thiourea as Masking Agent

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A complexometric method for the determination of Tl^{III} in the presence of other metal ions is described based on the selective masking ability of thiourea towards Tl^{III} at pH 5.0–6.0 (hexamine). Thallium(III) and diverse metal ions are initially complexed with a known excess of EDTA and the surplus EDTA is titrated with standard zinc sulphate solution using xylenol orange as indicator. An excess of thiourea solution (10%) is then added, and the EDTA released from the Tl^{III}-EDTA complex is titrated against zinc sulphate solution. The method proposed is accurate (3–92 mg Tl) with relative errors $\leq 0.13\%$ and standard deviations ≤ 0.03 mg. This method is applied to the determination of Tl in its alloy compositions and its complexes.

Thallium has been selectively determined by EDTA using masking and demasking techniques¹. Here, selective decomposition of the Tl^{III}-EDTA complex by the addition of thiourea solution at pH 5.0–6.0 and at room temperature is described. This reagent can quantitatively reduce Tl^{III}-EDTA complex, giving Tl^I that shows little tendency for complexation in the above pH range.

Results and Discussion

The reaction tendency of metals which shows different oxidation states, are entirely different, hence masking can be effectively achieved by the suitable oxidation or reduction of such species. Thallium is one such metal which forms a stable complex² with EDTA in +3 oxidation state and shows little tendency for complexation in +1 state³. Even if Tl^{III} forms a stable complex with EDTA it may do so only under high pH condition. Thiourea forms stable *s*-bonded complexes with soft metal ions⁴. The +1 oxidation state of thallium in the solution was confirmed by spot-test techniques⁵.

The determination of thallium in thallic nitrate solution shows that accurate and consistently reproducible results are obtainable within permissible errors. Thallium is determined in the range 3–92 mg in an aliquot.

The effect of different metal ions and anions on the quantitative determination of thallium(III) were studied with 15.37 mg of thallium(III) in solution. No interference was observed when the following ions were present; 100 mg of Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Pb^{II}; 40 mg of Al^{III}, Bi^{III}, Cr^{III}, Ce^{III}, La^{III}, V^{IV}, Ti^{IV} or Zr^{IV}; 8 mg of U^{VI}, Pt^{IV}, Fe^{III}, Ru^{III}, In^{III}, Rh^{III} or Ag^I; 100 mg of acetate, nitrate, sulphate, borate, phosphate, chloride, bromide or fluoride. Sn^{IV}, Hg^{II}, Pd^{II} and Cu^{II} interfered severely. The interference can be obviated by using suitable secondary masking. Relative errors in the above studies did not exceed $\pm 0.05\%$.

Applications : Thallium(I) complexes were prepared

from some sulfur donor ligands by conventional methods and their purity was checked from elemental analysis. The complex (0.2–0.4 g) was decomposed by evaporation to near dryness with aqua regia. The residue was then cooled, dissolved in 2 *N* HNO₃ (3 ml) and made up to 100 ml with distilled water. Aliquots (10 ml) were used for titration as per the proposed method and the results are presented in Table 1. Various synthetic mixture of Tl with Ti, Zn, Pd or Bi metal ions were prepared corresponding to their alloy compositions and the Tl^{III} was determined using the proposed method (Table 2).

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF Tl COMPLEXES ($n = 3$)

Compd.	Tl present mg	Tl found mg	Relative error %
Tl(C ₃ H ₅ N ₄ S) ^a	61.30	61.35	+0.08
Tl(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ OS) ^b	46.51	46.59	+0.17
Tl(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S) ^c	46.97	46.89	-0.17

^aThallium complex of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4,-triazole.

^bThallium complex of 3-(*o*-tolylloxymethyl)-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole. ^cThallium complex of 4-benzylideneamino-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole.

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF Tl^{III} IN ARTIFICIAL MIXTURES OF SALTS CORRESPONDING TO ALLOY COMPOSITIONS ($n = 4$)

Mixture	Composition %	Tl found %	Relative error %
Tl + Ti	20 + 80	19.96	-0.20
Tl + Zr	50 + 50	50.06	+0.12
Tl + Pd ^a	50 + 50	49.95	-0.10
Tl + Bi	75 + 25	74.91	+0.12

^aDL-Methionine used to mask Pd^{II}.

The method is simple and rapid, as it does not require heating, readjustment of pH and standardization of EDTA. The lack of effect of foreign ions on the accuracy and pre-

cision of the method reveals that the method may be suitable for the determination of Tl in its alloys.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical or pure grade. Thallous nitrate solution was prepared from thallic nitrate and standardized⁶. A 0.02 M zinc sulphate solution was prepared in distilled water and standardized⁸. EDTA solution (~0.04 M) was prepared in distilled water. Thiourea (10%) solution was prepared in hot distilled water. A 0.05% aqueous solution of xylenol orange indicator was used.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the acidic solution containing 3–92 mg Tl^{III}, a known volume of EDTA solution in excess of Tl present was added and diluted to 80–100 cm³. Solid hexamine was added to maintain pH 5.0–6.0. Xylenol orange was then added and the excess EDTA titrated against standard zinc sulphate solution. A 10% solution of thiourea was added (2.0 ± 0.2 ml for 15.37 mg of Tl^{III}) and the EDTA released was titrated against standard zinc sulphate solution. The second titre volume is equivalent to the

thallium(III) present.

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